

ADULT SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Annotation: *This article focuses on the advantages of adults in Second language learning. Mostly we think that only children have some critical period to learn language. However, in this article it is proven that adulthood is also a super period to learn languages. Moreover, adult learners can achieve more success in learning languages with getting more information in a short time rather than children who learn language more slowly.*

Key words: *adulthood, critical period, cognitive abilities, analyzing logically, environment, second language, teaching adults, cognitive level, motivation, super period.*

Introduction

By searching on research I have found that there are few scientific works on Adult second language acquisition which makes conducting research on this theme challenging. In spite of this I have decided to do my article on this topic because of the fact that I have a lot of adult learners. Most people think that learning a foreign language is much more difficult for adults rather than children or teens. Since childhood is considered to have some critical period.

However, as a tutor I have a number of language learners who began learning English as an adult and achieved high success such as going to university or getting high scores in the IELTS exam. Also, I am going to prove that adult learners can be the best learners and adulthood is the super time in human's life to increase one's perspective through learning other languages. Most adults give up learning languages because of some negative thoughts and experiences by others without thinking that adults may have some advantages to learn languages which younger generations have no [2].

The period of adulthood is the absolutely perfect time to broaden one's horizon by learning other languages. However, in most cases adult learners have negative thoughts that they cannot achieve success in learning because of the fact that they are already grown up and last their critical period. In another case adults come to the conclusion that they cannot

study foreign languages for their other adult friends and couldn't achieve success in learning [9]. But they don't know that they create critical periods with their motivation, with their planned purposes in life. It is never late to begin learning a second language. Especially adults can do this since they have very hot blood which encourages them to act like heroes in any field of life. So they are able to be heroes of language learners of any age.

The most important thing is that beginning well means half done as Aristotle mentioned. So, any age is not late to learn languages since any age has its own advantages. For example, adults have their own advantages in learning a second language. Even though teaching adults and teaching children seems to be the same, in fact there is a big difference. Firstly, as adults have stronger cognitive ability than children, they are able to catch on what you teach or explain quickly. Despite the fact that adults are shier than children, they can feel so confident which children can't. Plus, teaching adults can be easier since they are able to understand abstract rules. But if there isn't real life language, it may be too boring for adults too.

It is said that adults are able to concentrate on even what they are not really interested in. But as usual keeping activities short and fun is better. You shouldn't forget one thing, dealing with adults is absolutely different from dealing with children, adults hate being treated like children are treated, for instance, being called "Kid" "child" etc... Don't laugh at adults if they do something wrong, because they feel awkward themselves. Especially do not ignore them [10]. During teaching adults, create a friendly environment, ask ideas or ask their opinions. So, you shouldn't treat adults like you treat little children. Because they are adults and they want to feel respectful, grown up and so on. So, make them feel they are independent individuals too.

Literature Review

It is not a challenge for adult learners to learn another language. Because of getting older, adults gain experience and knowledge day by day. That's why their level to learn a new thing, analyzing logically, the ability to control themselves serves the adults as a helpful tool to acquire a new language than they can do for younger children [1]. While adults learn a foreign language, their cognitive level is improved, and their view becomes mature. This cognitive level is divided into three phases. First phase involves inner-sense and perceiving static, but children's language cannot understand the importance of this and logical shift. In the next second phase, children's language begins improving, that's why they can avoid the barriers which they face in the first phase. The final stage, which is

a more advanced phase of adults' cognitive abilities, is much more complicated one. According to McKay H. & Tom, A. (1999) the explanations which are based on grammar, may be much easier to comprehend for adults, however, children may face challenges when they have to do them on their own.

If there are lots of advantages for adults than younger children, having logical thought can be one important one of them [9]. As adults are growing their level at thinking is improved and it can be helpful to think more logically, to have powerful skill to analyze and to make conclusions of things that they learned; and they become advantageous to work with grammar rules and expressing the sentences that give chance to solve problems without difficulties [3]. However, as we think, most children have not only the knowledge that they went through, but also they can develop understanding comprehensively what they learned. These things, namely, the ability and knowledge to gain information can affect adults very well on adults to learn a new language [4].

While children are learning a second language, self-monitoring of adults is strong. In their age they began to analyze, rectify their mistakes which they are doing when they are in this process [8]. Because they have different characteristics at different ages, they think differently and it doesn't stay without affecting their learning method. And also, adults are so sociable to participate in discussions. While children cannot learn a new language actively because of not enough autonomy, adults can do that with great purpose and interest [5]. If they fail, they do not stop and they put effort and carry on learning, motivating them with a positive outcome.

Even though adults can learn another language easily, it doesn't mean they can do that in every period of their life. After some time, they may lose most skills they had when they were adults. According to some linguists, despite the fact that adults put a lot of effort and energy into learning a second language, they cannot acquire it perfectly [7]. Scientists defined the connection between adult's age and learning a new language. This is one of the important factors to learn language. Some critics said that the most available time to learn language is when children are at their 2 years old minimum and maximum till their puberty begins. In this time, children can learn better than any other period of their life. Because the best time to learn a new language was passed, after puberty it is nearly impossible for children to acquire it [1].

Yeah, maybe they can learn, but they have problems. For example, they have not fluency while speaking and not good pronunciation, or they

may face some problems with their grammar, even though they learned it for a long time [2]. So we should accept the fact that, before the period of puberty, every adult can learn second language without most challenges, but after the puberty, it may be very difficult because, after this period they lose their fresh ability to learn new things, their brain become bigger and it may have influence on children's psychology [6].

As well as age, environment can also have an effect on learning a new language. Perhaps children cannot know the grammar of their native language perfectly, but they can speak in this language fluently. Because, since they were born, people who live in the surrounding of this child speak in this native language [8]. This is why the child hears it a lot, thinks in this language and automatically it affects children's speaking [9]. That's why it is hard to learn a second language, namely there is not much, or even nobody to speak in this other language. Nevertheless, most language learners keep studying.

Although people have a device to learn language when they are children, it weakens when they become adult when they are born they have a system based on their native grammar [1]. So, when we were children, we were not taught how to speak, following grammar rules, because it has been put already in our brain, resulting in second language learners having to learn everything in this language to acquire it perfectly, while the native have not to do these efforts.

There is a famous saying "Well begun is half done". The thing which I was going to say is that adults should begin learning language positively with good thought, encouraging motivations aiming for a happy ending. So, human psychology also plays a very important role in adult second language acquisition [9]. If you are a university student and want to learn foreign language spend a little time day by day without making pressure to yourself on top of homework such as reading materials and writing tasks: The most important thing one should not stop some days after beginning To achieve high result There shouldn't be pauses in spite of spending a little time. Continuous attempts give us the perfect result which we expected.

Arkady Gilberman (2019) argues adults learn new languages with difficulty rather than children because children learn new languages like their native language without grammar without being able to read and write. However, adults cannot learn like this because of the fact that they have already had grammar, writing, reading skills in their native. So they begin to compare their native language and forget language. Nevertheless, this comparison is one of the advantages of adult learners

which means that adults can accept more information than children in a short time. For example, children listen to the forgotten language a year and then begin to speak like their native language. As for adults, they are much faster because of their grown up mind. So, Adults are able to develop both their listening and speaking at the same time because of their life experience [1]. Teaching or explaining something to adults is easier since their understanding skill is much more developed than children. Teachers have to repeat simple things hundreds of times for children in order to make them understand, however this process can be understandable.

Learner's Profile

The Subject of my research is a 20 year old female student of mine who studies IELTS in my privately teaching lessons.

Her name is Zahro who began learning English when she was 18 years old. In the beginning, she came to me saying that she wants to learn English so that she can enter the university. She grew up in a family that speaks only uzbek and didn't study English in her school period too. But she had good knowledge in her native uzbek, besides she studied all other school subjects except English Because of the fact that she has no opportunity to study English. To tell the truth, she was really energetic. All though I gave her a lot of homework to do she was always ready to be active. She always compared English grammar with uzbek grammar and this helped her to understand better.

At first, she learned only grammar in that her purpose was to be a university student and our state test system demands only grammar for universities. After learning English for a year with strong hard work she had enough grammar knowledge on English and was able to enter Karshi state University to the faculty of English philology.

However, after being a student she didn't stop learning English she went on to learn English for IELTS. I can't say that all adults have the motivation to learn like Zahro, but I was really surprised at her energy. Even I took energy from her study. After a year she took overall 6 bands from IELTS. On top of this she hasn't stopped studying yet in order to get a much higher score from IELTS.

Research Design

In this project I have tried to find out what kind of features helped the subject to learn language fast and what can be the cause of her achievement which can be a good lesson for others who want to learn foreign languages as adults.

Firstly, I would prefer to interview the subject in order to know about things she paid attention to during the period of learning English. How was her background knowledge when she began to study the English language. So I prepared some questions in advance to ask her about.

Secondly, I will give the subject the tasks of writing an essay on the theme "The factors that helped me to learn English fast". This essay is considered to define the learner's motivation, hard work and features which are important for adult foreign language learners who are confused to take up learning foreign language.

Finally, I would like to check the subject's critical thinking. So I will give her one of the IELTS reading passages with 13 reading comprehension questions. Besides, I will give her another task on this passage. It will be writing the summary of this passage.

Data collection

The data collection began making up questions for the subject.

The questions are considered as the first part of the research and they include questions about the learner's background, the motivation that encouraged her, extra activities which she used during learning, her plans and purpose for the future, learning upsides and downsides relating to her age.

From the subject's answers to the questions it is clear that she had no any English knowledge before beginning to learn English. However she had great motivation which always influenced her. She liked reading books in her native language. She read originally uzbek books, but as for foreign literature she was able to read only uzbek translations of them. So, she had a desire to be able to read great treasures of the world literature in an original version (she meant most of them were English origin novels). This encouraged her to take first steps for the English language. Besides, when the subject went to Samarkand, which is the historical city of Uzbekistan, with her classmates she saw a lot of tourists there. At that time the dream about being able to communicate with tourists in English appeared to her.

She is the girl who does her best for future plans and purposes so strict plans and exact purposes give her motivation to go forward.

The second observation was that the subject should write an essay on the topic "The factors that helped me to learn English fast". It is clear that her essay is well-organized and consists of very clear ideas. We can see a wide range of vocabulary, good grammar, connected ideas in her essay. According to the requirements the essay should contain at least 200 words,

however, she wrote about 300 words, which means she has abundant ideas and strong desire to write, to my mind.

Because when she was handing me in her essay she said that she enjoyed writing an essay on that topic and it was very interesting for her.

The third observation showed the subject's thinking degree as well as reading skills. It is clear that her critical thinking ability is very good. So she was able to find 12 true answers out of 13 reading passage questions, which means her reading skills are also very good.

Moreover, the summary which the subject wrote is to a high degree she could explain the meaning of the passage using necessary linking words and synonyms in an excellent way. The general meaning of paragraphs are joined without missing any important feature.

Conclusion

Now that we have observed the whole data carefully about the subject one can conclude the adults can learn any foreign language effectively since they are strong enough with a wide range of vocabulary and high level of understanding about the language system. They can compare their target language with their native language. Because of the fact that they have enough grammar knowledge in their native language and ability to understand wider schemes they can accept more information. Adults are not satisfied with only teachers or instructors, they can do extra activities to improve and they are clever enough to find better ways to achieve success. I think I have been able to prove that there is no age limit to learn foreign language at any age.

Adulthood gives some advantages for adults to learn languages which people in other ages don't have. Adults shouldn't take into consideration some wrong myths that adult learners are not able to acquire their target language as children do easily. On the contrary, there are a lot of examples which prove that adults can learn foreign languages even more easily than children.

One can learn a second language if there is a wish. No obstacles can prevent from achieving success if one has a strong desire, planned purpose and right way.

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